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Innovative use of botanical extract *Pelargonium graveolens* as an eco-friendly biopesticide against fall armyworm *Spodoptera frugiperda* (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae)

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Abstract

Maize (*Zea mays* L.) is one of the most important strategic crops in Egypt; however, its productivity is severely threatened by the fall armyworm *Spodoptera frugiperda* (J.E. Smith) (Lepidoptera, Noctuidae). This study aimed to evaluate the bio-toxicity of *Pelargonium graveolens* extracts (Flowers and leaves) against *S. frugiperda* larvae. Results revealed that flower extract exhibited higher larvicidal activity than leaf extract, with 70% concentrations causing near-complete mortality after seven days (95.2% for flowers and 91.9% for leaves). Biochemical analysis showed marked reductions in protein and lipid contents in treated larvae, accompanied by esterase inhibition and elevated peroxidase activity, indicating a dual mode of action involving suppression of detoxification mechanisms and induction of oxidative stress. Histopathological examinations further demonstrated severe damage to the midgut epithelium and deformation of goblet cells compared to the control. Overall, the findings highlight that *P. graveolens*, particularly the phenol-rich flower extract, represents a promising eco-friendly candidate for IPM against *S. frugiperda*. Now, plant extract, especially *P. graveolens*, presents a promising avenue for eco-friendly pest control strategies against *S. frugiperda* on maize crops. This study is intended to generate foundational scientific data to support future researchers and practitioners in finding the most effective and sustainable botanical active ingredient for managing FAW infestations in Egyptian agro-ecosystems.

Introduction

In recent years, Insect pest infestations were have remained the biggest challenging to maize production in Egypt, limiting crop productivity and threatening food security. Among the wide range of insect pests infesting maize, only a few species inflict significant economic losses. Notably, fall armyworm (FAW), *Spodoptera frugiperda* (J.E. Smith) (Lepidoptera, Noctuidae), has emerged as

one of the most damaging invasive and destructive pests in recent years, exhibiting high adaptability and destructive feeding behavior. *S. frugiperda* was a polyphagous lepidopteran pest that prefers the Poaceae crops (Casmuz *et al.*, 2010). It is most commonly harboured by the grasses such as maize, rice, sorghum, and sugarcane. However, it was attacked by 353 host plant species principally Poaceae, Fabaceae, and Asteraceae plant families (Montezano *et*

al., 2018). Since its first detection in Africa in 2016, it has rapidly spread into Asia, causing considerable maize yield reductions and raising urgent concerns for integrated pest management strategies in Egypt and the MENA region (Goergen *et al.*, 2016; FAO, 2018, and Hassan *et al.*, 2024). Mohamed *et al.* (2022) first recorded this pest on maize in 2019 in Upper Egypt. After that, it rapidly dispersed to different countries in Egypt and caused serious injuries to more than 350 plant species (Mohamed *et al.*, 2022, and Dahi *et al.*, 2020). As well as maize, rice, wheat, sugar beet, soybean, cotton, potato, onion, and tomato (Montezano *et al.*, 2018, and CABI, 2018). FAW is a primary pest of maize; it can cause substantial yield losses (Hassan *et al.*, 2024). Previous studies have shown that in the absence of effective management strategies, *S. frugiperda* infestations can lead to yield reductions of up to 40% or more in maize-dominant systems (Chabi-Olaye *et al.*, 2005, and Kumela *et al.*, 2019). While Wondimu *et al.* (2021) reported that FAW is shown to devastate maize producing up to 71% yield losses. Chemical insecticides have led to widespread environmental contamination, and recent monitoring data reveal a significant accumulation of their residues (Manda *et al.*, 2020). Consequently, there has been growing interest in biological control approaches, particularly the use of plant-derived extracts against *S. frugiperda*. These botanical-based alternatives are well-suited for integration into Integrated Pest Management programs, as they tend to degrade more rapidly and pose less risk to beneficial insects compared to conventional chemical insecticides. Therefore, they are considered environmentally friendly strategies for sustainable pest control (Ignacimuthu and Vendan, 2008, and Archana *et al.*, 2022).

One of the management strategies for this destroyed pest is the use of botanical insecticides, including those derived from *Pelargonium graveolens*, which offer reduced risks to human health and the environment compared to chemical insecticides (Hernández-Juárez *et al.*, 2021, and Ngegba *et al.*,

2022). *P. graveolens*, commonly referred to as geranium, is widely valued for its essential oil, which contains a high concentration of bioactive constituents (Kačániová *et al.*, 2023). Interestingly, they found that the chemical constituents of *P. graveolens* essential oils, especially geraniol, had antioxidant, antibacterial, antimicrobial, antibiofilm, and insecticidal activities (Niculau *et al.*, 2013, and Kačániová *et al.*, 2023). They also reported that the mortality rate of geraniol, β -Citronellol, citral, and linalool components in *P. graveolens* extracts was significantly recorded about 30, 29.7, 64, and 90% on *S. frugiperda* larvae (Niculau *et al.*, 2013).

In addition, Diédhiou *et al.* (2021) found that geraniol reduced the *S. frugiperda* infestation rate up to 38.5%. Essential oils, particularly those derived from geranium, have exhibited insecticidal action against various pests, it is including bio-active ingredient such as linalool, 1,8-cineole, geraniol, citral, carvone, limonene, and Azamax had severe toxicity against the 3rd larval instar of *S. frugiperda* (Niculau *et al.*, 2013). They detected a low LD₅₀ and LD₉₀ (1.13 and 2.56 μ g/mg/ insect) on FAW. Many issues have resulted from the fact that the plant-derived pesticides were an important tactic in the suggestion of *S. frugiperda* management tactics, as well as Corassa *et al.* (2022) used plant extracts, *Chrysanthemum morifolium*, *Sansevieria trifasciata*, *Tagetes erecta*, and *Dieffenbachia picta* for controlling *S. frugiperda*. Additionally, Ngegba *et al.* (2022) evaluated the pesticides-based plant-extracts, such as *Eucalyptus globulus* and *Azadirachta indica*, against FAW as sustainable alternatives to traditional pesticides. Moreover, uses of different plant-derived insecticides in controlling FAW, like osthole extract (Idrees *et al.*, 2023) and botanical powders of *Ruta*

graveolens, *Phoradendron densum*, and *Larrea tridentata* against 1st larval instar of the fall armyworm (Hernández-Juárez *et al.*, 2021). Additionally, Corzo-Gómez *et al.* (2024) stated that a group of coumarin derivatives had highly effective insect growth regulatory activity and adult deformities against this pest. In contrast, plumbagin, or naphthoquinone, was a phytochemical organic compound, that was derived from *Plumbago zeylanica*, had highly larvicidal activity against FAW infestations (Sun *et al.*, 2024) and on various stored-product and agricultural pests, indicating its important role in botanical pest management strategies (Usha Rani, 2012). On the other hand, Negrini *et al.* (2019) evaluated the essential oils of *Piper umbellatum*, *Myrciaria dubia*, *Lippia microphylla*, and *Corymbia citriodora* as bioactive agents for *S. Frugiperda*. They recorded that these plant extracts caused the mortality rate in the FAW population above 80% in the laboratory.

Furthermore, *P. graveolens* extract demonstrates a highly significant potential as an insect control agent in the management of *S. frugiperda*, the observed variability in its insecticidal efficacy and the limited understanding of its environmental implications highlight the necessity for further research to optimize its use within integrated pest management programs. Therefore, it is urgent to evaluate the effectiveness of *P. graveolens* leaf and flower extracts as innovative green biopesticides against *S. frugiperda* and environmentally friendly botanical insecticides under laboratory conditions.

This study is intended to generate valuable scientific data to support future researchers and practitioners in finding the most effective and sustainable botanical active ingredient

for managing FAW infestations in Egyptian maize cultivations.

Materials and methods

Toxicity of botanical extract, *Pelargonium graveolens* on *Spodoptera frugiperda* larvae:

1. *Spodoptera frugiperda* culture:

A laboratory colony of FAW, *S. frugiperda* larvae, was reared on fresh castor leaves, *Ricinus communis*, till the pupation progress in an incubator at 25±2°C and 70±5% RH. FAW culture was carried out at the plant protection research institute; larvae were reared in a rectangle-shaped plastic box (25 cm length x 15 cm width x 10 cm height) covered by cotton clothes and contained a thin layer of tissue put on the bottom for moisture absorbers. Pupae were kept in glass jars (20 cm length X 8 cm diameter) containing an amount of sawdust to absorb the moisture until the adult's emergence. Newly emerged adults were fed a 50% (w/v) honeybee solution delivered via a cotton pad soaked in the solution at the same conditions of temperature and RH% as larvae. The folded paper sheet in a zigzag shape was placed inside each glass jar to facilitate oviposition by the adult females. A glass jar was covered by a piece of cloth and secured with rubber bands, this jar was inspected at a day intervals to replace the sheet of oviposition with new ones and renew the feeding solution. Egg masses were maintained in the previously used plastic box and monitored until hatching. A laboratory strain of *S. frugiperda* was maintained through at least six generations in an incubator set at 25±2°C and 70±5% relative humidity to ensure sensitivity to experimental treatments.

2. Toxicity of botanical extract, *Pelargonium graveolens* flowers and leaves:

A laboratory bioassay was carried out at the Plant Protection Research Institute (PPRI) to determine the

insecticidal efficacy of *P. graveolens* flower and leaf extracts against the 2nd and 4th larval instar of *S. frugiperda*. Fresh flowers and leaf plants were collected. The plant parts were washed, shade-dried, and ground into a fine powder. The extract was prepared using absolute methanol solvent extraction at the Insect Physiology Department, PPRI, followed by filtration and evaporation to obtain the crude extract.

A dipping technique using castor leaves was employed to apply treatments against the 2nd and 4th larval instars of *S. frugiperda*. Bioassay was applied in plastic containers (9 cm × 8 cm × 4 cm) to test six concentrations (5, 10, 15, 25, 50, and 70% of the chosen *P. graveolens* flowers and leaves), against larvae. To minimize larval cannibalism, each larva was treated individually in a separate, previously plastic box. For each concentration, three replicates were used, each containing 10 larvae. Prior to treatment, fresh castor leaves were dipped in the respective concentration of each tested compound for 30 seconds. The control group (untreated) or the check treatment was treated with distilled water. The numbers of live and dead 2nd and 4th instar of *S. frugiperda* larvae were daily recorded for 10 days after treatment. Subsequently, surviving larvae from each treatment were individually transferred to previously used plastic boxes under controlled laboratory conditions (25 ± 2°C and 70 ± 5% RH). Corrected mortality percentages were calculated using Abbott's formula (Abbott, 1925). Lethal concentrations (LC₅₀ and LC₉₀), toxicity index (TI), and resistance ratio (RR) values were determined using the Ldp-line software (Bakr, 2007), which conducts probit analysis in accordance with Finney (1971) to establish dose–response regression lines and evaluate toxicological parameters. The toxicity index of the tested compounds was

calculated using Sun's equation (1950) as:

$$\text{Toxicity index (TI)} = \frac{\text{LC}_{50} \text{ the most toxic compound}}{\text{LC}_{50} \text{ of the other compared tested compound}} \times 100$$

To evaluate the effect of this plant-derived extract from leaves and flowers on the larvae, samples were collected one day after treatment. Mid-gut sections were prepared for histological examination at the Zoology Department, Faculty of Science, Menofia University. Additionally, the bioactive components of the plant extract were identified by using Gas Chromatography–Mass Spectrometry (GC–MS) at the Faculty of Science, Alexandria University. The data obtained was statistically analyzed using the SAS software (SAS, 2004), applying analysis of variance (ANOVA) and F-tests. Mean comparisons were performed using the Least Significant Difference (LSD) test at a 0.05 level of probability. Lethal concentrations (LC₅₀ and LC₉₀), slope values, and chi-square (χ^2) statistics were estimated using the Ldp-line software (Bakr, 2007) based on probit analysis according to the method of Finney (1971).

Results and discussion

1. Toxicity of botanical extract, *Pelargonium graveolens* flowers and leaves against *Spodoptera frugiperda* larvae :

A controlled laboratory bioassay was conducted to investigate the insecticidal activity of *P. graveolens* (Flowers and leaves) extract against 2nd and 4th instar larvae of *S. frugiperda* at different concentrations (Tables 1 and 2). In case of the 4th larval instar, the results revealed a significant positive correlation between larval mortality and both exposure duration and extract concentration, indicating that increased concentration and prolonged exposure markedly enhanced the efficacy of the *P. graveolens* extract against *S.*

frugiperda larvae. In Table (1), the 4th larval mortality at early days after treatment remained low at lower concentrations, while significant increases occurred from 4th day onwards in higher concentrations, implying a delayed toxic effect possibly associated with ingestion-mediated mortality (Miresmailli and Isman, 2014). Furthermore, the results indicated a clear dose-dependent increase in mortality of 4th instar larvae of *S. frugiperda* when treated with both *P. graveolens* flower and leaf extracts. The highest mortality rates were consistently observed at 50% and 70% concentrations for both extracts, with flower extract showing slightly higher cumulative efficacy than leaf extract. At 50% and 70% concentrations, the *P. graveolens* flower extract achieved accumulated mortality rates of 88.6% and 78.6%, respectively. These were statistically superior to the lower concentrations (5–25%), indicating a strong positive correlation between concentration and mortality ($F = 69.2$, $LSD = 8.7$ at prob. < 0.01). Similarly, the *P. graveolens* leaf extract at 70% resulted in 81.3% accumulated mortality, also significantly higher than the lower concentration treatments (Table 1). Notably, the *P. graveolens* flower extract at 50% concentration surpassed all others in mortality, suggesting the presence of potent bioactive compounds with systemic effects, possibly flavonoids, terpenoids, or alkaloids, as supported by previous issues (Isman, 2006, and Pavela and Benelli, 2016).

In view of the data tabulated in Table (2), both *P. graveolens* flower and leaf extracts at 70% concentration resulted in near-complete mortality after 7 days post-treatment (95.2% for flower and

91.9% for leaf extracts), highlighting the exceptional efficacy of *P. graveolens* treatments on early instars. Statistically, these effects were highly significant ($F = 29.9$, $LSD = 11.2$ and $p < 0.01$). Moreover, the mortality was increased at 4 days after treatment with all tested concentrations in the case of *P. graveolens* flower and leaf extracts. This data demonstrated that the 2nd larval instar was more susceptible than the 4th larval instar across all concentrations and treatments, consistent with known vulnerabilities in earlier larval stages due to thinner cuticle and less developed detoxification systems (Desneux *et al.*, 2007). At moderate concentrations (25–50%), the larval mortality was up to 50% at all investigated days post-treatment, furthermore, both *P. graveolens* extracts maintained a high accumulated mortality (>75%), suggesting practical field applicability in early infestations of *S. frugiperda*. Conversely, 5–10% concentrations were largely ineffective, especially the leaf extract at 5%, which only yielded 29.95–41.42% cumulative mortality for leaf and flower extracts, respectively (Table 2). This reinforces suitable concentration when using the *P. graveolens* botanical insecticides. The superior performance of flower-derived extracts might be due to higher concentrations of insecticidal phytochemicals, as supported by phytochemical analyses in similar species (Pavela, 2015). Accordingly, the present study demonstrated that *P. graveolens* extract possesses significant larvicidal activity of flower extract compared to leaf extract against *S. frugiperda* larvae, with mortality increasing in a dose- and time-dependent manner.

Table (1): Mortality % of 4th larval instar of FAW *Spodoptera frugiperda* after treated by botanical extract, *Pelargonium graveolens*.

Plant Extract	Conc.	Mortality % 4 th larval instar of <i>Spodoptera frugiperda</i> at DAT							
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Accumulate Mortality %
Flower	5%	10.0 e	10.0 e	10.0 e	30.0d	27.6e	27.6ef	35.7e	21.5f
	10%	10.0 e	10.0 e	20.0de	40.0d	37.9e	37.9e	35.7e	27.4 ef
	15%	30.0 cd	50.0cd	60.0b	60.0c	58.6d	58.6d	57.1d	53.5d
	25%	40.0 c	40.0d	40.0c	70.0bc	69.0cd	69.0cd	89.3ab	59.6d
	50%	80.0 a	80.0a	80.0a	90.0a	96.6a	96.6a	96.4a	88.6a
	70%	60.0 b	60.0bc	60.0b	80.0ab	96.6a	96.6a	96.4a	78.6bc
Leaf	5%	10.0 e	10.0 e	10.0e	10.0e	6.9f	17.2f	14.3 f	11.2g
	10%	20.0 de	20.0e	20.0de	40.0d	37.9e	37.9e	46.4de	31.8e
	15%	10.0 e	10.0 e	30.0cd	40.0d	37.9e	37.9e	46.4de	30.3e
	25%	40.0 c	60.0bc	60.0b	60.0c	58.6d	69.0cd	78.6bc	61.0d
	50%	60.0 b	60.0bc	70.0ab	70.0bc	79.3bc	79.3bc	71.4c	70.0c
	70%	70.0 ab	70.0ab	80.0a	80.0ab	89.7ab	89.7ab	89.3ab	81.3ab
F value		19.8	21.3	21.0	17.2	25.9	23.7	36.6	69.2
Prob.<[F]		16.9	16.9	16.9	16.9	16.7	16.7	13.3	8.7

DAT= Day after treatment Prob.= Probability FAW= Fall armyworm Conc.= Concentration

Means signed by the same letter in the same column were non-significant

Table (2): Mortality % of 2nd larval instar of FAW *Spodoptera frugiperda* after treated by botanical extract *Pelargonium graveolens*.

Plant Extract	Conc.	Mortality % 2 nd larval instar of <i>Spodoptera frugiperda</i> at DAT							
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Accumulate Mortality %
Flower	5%	23.3e	20.7e	24.1d	42.9cd	55.6cd	53.8cd	64.0bc	41.4e
	10%	23.3e	20.7e	34.8cd	54.2bc	68.1bc	67.5bc	65.6bc	47.7e
	15%	43.3cd	62.2cd	76.3ab	80.0a	86.3ab	86.3ab	85.2ab	74.2d
	25%	53.3c	51.9d	55.6bc	86.7a	93.3a	93.3a	96.3a	75.8cd
	50%	73.3b	72.6bc	76.3ab	93.3a	96.8a	96.7a	96.7a	86.5abc
	70%	93.3a	93.3a	93.3a	96.7a	96.7a	96.8a	96.8a	95.2a
Leaf	5%	23.3e	20.7e	24.1d	21.4d	33.3d	42.3d	40.0c	30.0f
	10%	33.3de	31.0e	34.8cd	54.2bc	68.1bc	67.5bc	77.8ab	52.4e
	15%	23.3e	20.7e	45.2cd	54.2bc	68.1bc	65.4bc	77.8ab	51.0e
	25%	53.3c	72.6bc	76.3ab	75.8ab	86.3ab	93.3a	96.3a	79.1bcd
	50%	73.3b	72.6bc	86.7a	86.7a	96.8a	96.7a	96.7a	87.0ab
	70%	83.3ab	83.0ab	93.3a	93.3a	96.7a	96.8a	96.8a	91.9a
F value		133.3	20.3	11.6	10.0	6.2	6.3	4.3	29.9
Prob.<[F]		19.5	17.9	22.8	22.1	23.43	21.9	25.1	11.2

DAT= Day after treatment Prob.= Probability FAW= Fall armyworm Conc.= Concentration

Means signed by the same letter in the same column were non-significant.

Furthermore, the results suggest the potential of *P. graveolens* as a sustainable botanical insecticide for inclusion in integrated pest management (IPM) programs, especially in light of increasing resistance of *S. frugiperda* to conventional synthetic insecticides (Goergen *et al.*, 2016 and Sisay *et al.*, 2019). However, further studies are

recommended to evaluate its field efficacy, potential phytotoxicity, and compatibility with other IPM components. Results showed that the toxicity parameters of *P. graveolens* flower and leaf extracts against 4th instar larvae of *S. frugiperda* are presented in Table (3). The LC₅₀ value in the case of flower extract for 4th instar larvae was more effective than leaf

extract after seven days of treatment. The lowest value of LC₅₀ was 10.09% at 7 days after treatment (DAT) with flower extract. Whereas, it was the lowest value being 14.74% at 7 DAT with leaf extract. On all days after

treatment, the LC₅₀ value was lower with flower extract than the leaf extract, except at 3 DAT, the leaf extract (24.56%) is slightly efficient than the flower extract (25.67%) against 4th instar larvae of *S. frugiperda*.

Table (3): Toxicity of *Pelargonium graveolens* extract against 4th larval instar of FAW *Spodoptera frugiperda*.

Plant extract	Stage	DAT	LC ₅₀	LC ₉₀	Toxicity Index*	RR**	Slope	Slope +/-	R.P.***	χ ²	Prob.
Flower extract	4 th Larval instar	1 DAT	32.65	171.29	30.90	3.24	1.78	0.29	1.16	7.76	0.1
		2 DAT	29.07	177.05	34.72	2.88	1.63	0.28	1.30	13.32	0.01
		3 DAT	25.67	197.96	39.31	2.54	1.45	0.26	1.47	14.93	0.005
		4 DAT	11.70	88.10	86.26	1.16	1.46	0.27	3.23	3.30	0.51
		5 DAT	14.84	46.98	68.02	1.47	2.56	0.32	2.55	16.75	0.002
		6 DAT	11.85	51.88	85.15	1.17	2.00	0.31	3.19	3.43	0.86
		7 DAT	10.09	40.62	100	1	2.12	0.33	3.75	6.26	0.18
Leaf extract	4 th Larval instar	1 DAT	37.84	210.38	26.67	3.75	1.72	0.29	1.00	4.52	0.34
		2 DAT	32.84	179.88	30.73	3.25	1.74	0.28	1.15	9.14	0.06
		3 DAT	24.56	113.57	41.09	2.43	1.93	0.29	1.54	1.53	0.82
		4 DAT	20.28	125.71	49.75	2.01	1.62	0.27	1.87	2.48	0.62
		5 DAT	18.99	76.71	53.14	1.88	2.11	0.3	1.99	2.35	0.67
		6 DAT	16.43	79.14	61.44	1.63	1.88	0.28	2.30	1.78	0.78
		7 DAT	14.74	81.61	68.47	1.46	1.72	0.28	2.57	6.42	0.17

Toxicity Index* compared with LC₅₀ of flower extract against 4th larval instar of FAW at 7 DAT, DAT = Day After Treatment Resistance Ratio (RR**) compared with LC₅₀ of flower extract against 4th larval instar of FAW at 7 DAT Prob.= probability Relative potency (R.P.) *** compared with LC₅₀ of leaf extract against 4th larval instar of FAW at 1 DAT FAW = Fall armyworm.

The LC₉₀ values for the *Pelargonium graveolens* flower extract ranged from 40.62% to 197.96%, whereas those for the leaf extract extended from 76.71% to 210.38% (Table 3). The toxicity index compared with the LC₅₀ of flower extract as highly efficacy against the 4th larval instar of FAW at 7 DAT was 26.67-100%. Whereas, the Resistance ratio (RR) indicated that flower extract is more efficacy than leaf extract when compared with the LC₅₀ of flower extract against 4th larval instar of FAW at 7 DAT, moreover, Relative potency (R.P.) when compared with the LC₅₀ of leaf extract as the lowest efficacy against 4th larval instar of FAW at 1 DAT. The slope of the regression line was steeper for the flower extract (Extended from 1.45 ± 0.26-2.56±0.32) than the leaf extract (1.62 ± 0.27 to 2.11±0.3) against the 4th instar, indicating a greater response of flower extract against 4th instar larvae (Table 3). In summary, the flower extract of *P. graveolens* exhibited greater toxic

efficacy against fourth instar larvae of *S. frugiperda* compared to the leaf extract after 7 days post-treatment. In view of the data presented in Table (4), similar to the case of the 4th larval instar, the flower extract is more efficacy than the leaf extract of *P. graveolens*. The LC₅₀ and LC₉₀ were lower values for flower extract, representing 3.53-18.64% and 25.12-97.73% against the 2nd larval instar of *S. frugiperda*, respectively. In addition, the toxicity index and resistance ratio showed that the flower extract was more toxic against the second larval instar at 7 DAT than the leaf extract. Subsequently, the flower extract of *Pelargonium graveolens* exhibited greater toxic efficacy against the 2nd and 4th instar larvae of *S. frugiperda*. These results demonstrated that *Pelargonium graveolens* extract is more toxic to early instars of *S. frugiperda*, highlighting the importance of targeting earlier larval stages for more effective control.

Table (4): Toxicity of *Pelargonium graveolens* extract against 2th larval instar of FAW *Spodoptera frugiperda*.

Plant extract	Stage	DAT	LC ₅₀	LC ₉₀	Toxicity Index*	RR**	Slope	Slope +/-	R.P.***	χ ²	Prob.
Flower extract	2 nd Larval instar	1	18.6	97.73	18.96	5.27	1.78	0.28	1.1	4.83	0.31
		2	17.4	92.3	20.25	4.94	1.77	0.28	1.2	9.1	0.06
		3	13.1	84.46	26.94	3.71	1.59	0.27	1.6	10.3	0.03
		4	6.3	49.12	56.43	1.77	1.43	0.3	3.4	4.34	0.36
		5	4.28	25.49	82.49	1.21	1.66	0.35	5.0	1.42	0.84
		6	4.55	26.29	77.72	1.29	1.68	0.34	4.7	1.5	0.83
		7	3.53	25.12	100	1	1.51	0.34	6.0	3.84	0.43
Leaf extract		1	21.4	145.1	16.45	6.08	1.56	0.27	1.0	5.3	0.26
		2	20.0	116.2	17.6	5.68	1.68	0.27	1.0	9.26	0.06
		3	13.7	60.46	25.64	3.9	2.0	0.29	1.5	2.17	0.71
		4	11.5	58.01	30.48	3.28	1.83	0.29	1.8	1.5	0.83
		5	7.47	37.39	47.32	2.11	1.83	0.3	2.8	2.26	0.69
		6	6.39	38.23	55.31	1.81	1.65	0.33	3.3	3.5	0.48
		7	5.6	25.46	62.73	1.59	1.96	0.36	3.8	3.9	0.42

Toxicity Index* compared with LC₅₀ of flower extract against 2nd larval instar of FAW at 7 DAT, Resistance Ratio (RR**) compared with LC₅₀ of flower extract against 2nd larval instar of FAW at 7 DAT, Relative potency (R.P.) *** compared with LC₅₀ of leaf extract against 2nd larval instar of FAW at 1 DAT

The findings of this study provide compelling evidence for the insecticidal efficacy of *P. graveolens* extracts against *S. frugiperda* larvae, particularly at higher concentrations. The significant mortality rates observed suggest that this botanical species holds considerable promise as a plant-derived bio-insecticide. This is especially relevant in the context of rising resistance of *S. frugiperda* to conventional chemical insecticides, a challenge that has been widely reported across various regions (Goergen *et al.*, 2016 and Sisay *et al.*, 2019). Incorporating *P. graveolens* into Integrated Pest Management (IPM) could enhance sustainability and reduce environmental and health hazards associated with synthetic pesticide overuse. Generally, botanical insecticides are biodegradable with minimal risk to non-target organisms and are more acceptable to organic agriculture systems (Isman, 2006 and Pavela and Benelli, 2016). Additionally, Corzo-Gómez *et al.* (2024) and Sun *et al.* (2024) stated that plant extracts had highly effective larvicidal activity as insect growth regulatory activity and

adult deformities against this pest. Conversely, the botanical extract was effective on various stored-product and agricultural pests, indicating its important role in botanical pest management strategies (Usha Rani, 2012). Nevertheless, while the laboratory results are promising, several critical aspects require further investigation before field implementation. These include evaluating the extract's persistence and efficacy under variable environmental conditions, assessing potential phytotoxicity on treated crops, and examining these interactions with other IPM components. Such an issue would not only clarify the practical applicability of *P. graveolens* in real agricultural settings but also contribute to the broader goal of developing effective, low-risk alternatives to synthetic pesticides in managing *S. frugiperda* infestations.

2. Biochemical effect on *Spodoptera frugiperda* larvae after treated by *Pelargonium graveolens*:

Figure (1) illustrates the biochemical alterations in the

metabolites of *S. frugiperda* larvae following exposure to *P. graveolens* flower extract by $LC_{50} = 6.3\%$, as compared to the untreated control group. Non-significant reductions were observed in the contents of proteins and in treated larvae. Specifically, protein content in the 4th larval instar of *S. frugiperda* decreased from 4.14.67 mg/g b.wt in control to 364.56 mg/g b.wt in treated larvae ($t = 2.31$, $prob. = 0.08$), while lipid content decreased markedly from 330.33 mg/g b.wt to 285.56 mg/g b.wt ($t = 1.42$, $p = 0.2$). Such trends are consistent with previous reports indicating that sublethal exposure to plant-derived insecticides can impair nutrient assimilation and protein synthesis in lepidopteran pests, potentially through feeding inhibition and disruption of midgut digestive enzymes (Senthil-Nathan, 2013, and Koul, 2016). Data showed that the application of *P. graveolens* flower extract by $LC_{50} = 6.3\%$ on the 4th larval instar of *S. frugiperda* resulted in an obvious suppression of β -esterase activity (from 58.33 to 35.22 nmol/min/mg protein; $t = 6.46$, $p = 0.003$), suggesting disruption of detoxification pathways. Oppositely, the peroxidase activity increased significantly in treated larvae (from 0.43 to 0.83 nmol/min/mg protein; $t = 3.66$, $p = 0.02$), which likely signifies an activated oxidative stress response (Figure 1). β -esterases are crucial in the hydrolysis and detoxification of ester-containing xenobiotics, including synthetic and botanical insecticides (Li *et al.*, 2007). Suppression of this enzyme indicates potential inhibition of detoxification pathways, thereby increasing the

susceptibility of larvae to toxic compounds. Similar esterase inhibition has been documented in *S. frugiperda* following exposure to essential oils and phenolic-rich extracts, leading to enhanced toxicity (Gonçalves *et al.*, 2019). Conversely, peroxidase activity increased nearly twofold in treated larvae, suggesting an upregulated oxidative stress response. Peroxidases play a key role in scavenging reactive oxygen species (ROS) generated during oxidative stress, which can be induced by phenolic and terpenoid constituents of *P. graveolens* (Mishra *et al.*, 2020, and Pavela and Benelli, 2016). This enzymatic up regulation may represent a defensive adaptation to mitigate oxidative damage; however, persistent ROS production can overwhelm antioxidant defenses, leading to cellular damage and mortality (Felton and Summers, 1995). Overall, these findings suggest that *P. graveolens* flower extract exerts a dual mode of biochemical action in *S. frugiperda*: (1) suppression of detoxification mechanisms through esterase inhibition, and (2) induction of oxidative stress, as evidenced by elevated peroxidase activity. Such combined effects could reduce the pest's physiological capacity to tolerate and metabolize toxicants, making this extract a promising candidate for integration into eco-friendly pest management strategies. Further studies should focus on identifying the active phytochemicals responsible for these biochemical alterations and assessing their efficacy under field conditions.

Figure (1): Biochemical effect on *Spodoptera frugiperda* larvae after treated by botanical extract *Pelargonium graveolens*.

3. Histological structures on 4th larval instar of *Spodoptera frugiperda* after treated by LC₅₀ dose of *Pelargonium graveolens* flower and leaf extracts:

Figure (2) presents the transfer sections on the midgut of the 4th larval instar of *Spodoptera frugiperda* after exposure to the LC₅₀ dose of *P. graveolens* flower and leaf extracts. The midgut of larvae in the untreated control exhibited a normal histological architecture. The epithelial lining showed a clear organization, consisting of columnar and goblet cells. The lumen was encased by an intact peritrophic membrane, and both the circular and longitudinal muscle layers displayed normal structural integrity. Larvae treated with the LC₅₀ concentration of *P. graveolens* flower extract showed pronounced pathological changes in the midgut relative to the control. These included extensive vacuolation within columnar cell cytoplasm, disruption and loss of microvilli (MV), and progressive deterioration of the epithelial lining. Additionally, the presence of vesicle formation (VS) and cytoplasmic protrusions (CP) suggested compromised absorptive function and advanced cellular injury. These histopathological alterations align with earlier findings on lepidopteran larvae exposed to botanical extracts containing phenolic and terpenoid compounds. Such metabolites

have been reported to impair the peritrophic membrane, weaken the midgut barrier, and consequently diminish digestive performance (Rajashekar *et al.*, 2014; Pavela and Benelli, 2016 and Wahba *et al.*, 2022).

At the LC₅₀ concentration of the leaf extract (B), the midgut exhibited extensive structural damage. The epithelial lining was severely disrupted, with detached cells observed in the lumen, loss of tissue cohesion, and deformation of goblet cells. The connective tissue (CT) appeared disorganized and loosened, while regenerative cells (RC) were either markedly diminished or displayed abnormal morphology. The pathological features identified in the present study are in agreement with previously described mechanisms of toxicity in *Spodoptera* spp. following exposure to plant-derived insecticides, where oxidative stress and direct interactions of phytochemicals with cellular membranes were implicated (Nasr *et al.*, 2020; Senthil-Nathan *et al.*, 2012 and Wahba *et al.*, 2022).

The midgut alterations observed can be interpreted as the outcome of multiple concurrent toxicological processes: (i) destabilization of membrane structures by lipophilic constituents, (ii) oxidative injury associated with reactive oxygen species produced by phenolic compounds, and (iii) inhibition of

digestive enzyme activity, ultimately impairing nutrient uptake. Midgut histopathology therefore provides a reliable biomarker of botanical insecticide action, as these structural disturbances can substantially compromise larval feeding, retard growth, and lower survival (Morsi *et al.*, 2021 and Shah and Khan, 2014). Finally, control larvae showed normal midgut structure, whereas flower and leaf extracts caused severe epithelial disruption, cell detachment into the lumen, deformation of goblet cells, loosened connective tissue (CT), and reduced or abnormal regenerative cells (RC). In Tables (5 and 6), gas chromatography–mass spectrometry (GC–MS) analysis of *Pelargonium graveolens* leaf and flower extracts revealed appreciable differences in the qualitative and quantitative components. In leaf extracts, the most abundant components were bis(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate, 1,2-benzene dicarboxylic acid and 1,2,4-benzenetriol (50.69%), followed by tributyl acetylcitrate (16.37%), and notable amounts of pent-4-enoic acid derivatives and phytol isomers. These compounds include phthalates, fatty acid esters, and terpenoid derivatives, which are known for antioxidant, antimicrobial, and insecticidal activities (El-Seedi *et al.*, 2012 and Manandhar *et al.*, 2019). Also, phthalate derivatives have shown growth-inhibiting activity in lepidopteran larvae such as *Spodoptera* spp. and *Helicoverpa* spp., through their effect on insect hormonal processes (Zhang *et al.*, 2017). The relatively high proportion of plasticizer-type phthalates may originate from natural biosynthesis. Conversely, in Table (6), flower extracts were dominated by 1,2,3-benzenetriol (Pyrogallol) at 55.72%, followed by bis(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate (13.09%) and phenol, 3-pentadecyl- (5.53%) (Table 6). Pyrogallol and other phenolic compounds are potent antioxidants and have been reported to exhibit strong insecticidal and antimicrobial properties, potentially via

oxidative stress induction in target organisms (Mishra *et al.*, 2020). The presence of long-chain alkyl phenols, fatty acid derivatives, and terpenoid esters further supports the potential role of the flower extract as a source of multiple bioactive chemical classes. The compositional differences between leaves and flowers suggest organ-specific metabolic allocation in *P. graveolens*, possibly reflecting ecological roles in defense and pollinator attraction. Leaf extracts are richer in lipophilic esters and terpenoids, while flower extracts are phenolic-dominant. This variation is relevant for targeted applications—phenol-rich flower extracts may be more potent as contact insecticides or antioxidants, whereas the ester/terpenoid-rich leaf extracts may provide fumigant or repellent activity (Isman, 2020).

From an integrated pest management (IPM) perspective, the predominance of phenolic antioxidants in flowers and terpenoid esters in leaves suggests that whole-plant utilization could provide a broader spectrum of pest control mechanisms, combining contact toxicity, feeding deterrence, and antimicrobial protection. Future work should involve bioassays correlating these chemical profiles with specific pest mortality and sublethal effects, alongside safety evaluation for non-target organisms.

In conclusion, leaf extracts of *P. graveolens* are richer in lipophilic esters and terpenoids, while flower extracts of *P. graveolens* are phenolic-dominant. This variation is relevant for targeted applications—phenol-rich flower extracts may be more potent as contact insecticides or antioxidants, whereas the ester/terpenoid-rich leaf extracts may provide fumigant or repellent activity. So that, the utilization of *P. graveolens* extract presents a promising avenue for the development of eco-friendly pest control strategies against fall armyworm, *S. frugiperda*. Further research and field trials are necessary to optimize application methods and assess long-term efficacy.

A) Treated with Flower extract

B) Treated with Leaf extract

C) Control

Figure (2): Transverse section in the mid-gut of 4th larval instar of *Spodoptera frugiperda*, (C) untreated larvae, (A) treated with LC50 of flower extract, (B) treated with LC50 of leaf extract: Where, Circular muscle (CM); Longitudinal muscle (LM); Epithelial layer (EP); Columnar cells (CC); Connective tissue (CT); Regenerative cells (RC); Lumen (L); Peritrophic membrane (PM); Vesicles (VS); Microvilli (MV); Cytoplasmic protrusions (CP); Free cells (FC); Malpighian cell (MT); Goblet cell (GC).

Table (5): Leaf extract components of *Pelargonium graveolens* by using GC-MS analysis.

RT		Component	RT	Area %	Component
11.66	0.41	Ionone	29.57	0.35	2-oxabicyclo[3.3.0]oct-7-en-3-one,7-(1-hydroxypentyl)-
		3-buten-2-one,4-(2,6,6-trimethyl-2-cyclohexen-1-yl)-			9-methoxy-6-methyl-12,13-di oxo-tricyclo[7.3.1.01,6]tridecan-5-one
16.06	1.60	1,2,3-benzenetriol	29.91	3.14	cyclopentanebutanoic acid, 2-oxo-,methyl ester
16.18	0.61	1,2,3-benzenetriol			phytol isomer
16.29	1.09	1,2,4-benzenetriol	30.4	4.54	2-hexadecen-1-ol,3,7,11,15-tetramethyl-,[r-[r*,r*-(e)]]-
16.4	2.89	1,2,3-benzenetriol			pent-4-enoic acid,2-(2-hydroxy-3-isobutoxypropyl)-,hydrazide
17.02	0.48	1,2,4-benzenetriol			cis-9,10-epoxyoctadecanamide
17.19	0.73	1,2,4-benzenetriol			octadecanoic acid, 9,10-epoxy-,isopropyl ester
		2,4-octadienoic acid,7-hydroxy-6-methyl-, [r-[r*,s*-(e,e)]]-	isopropyl 8-(3-octyl-2-oxiranyl)octanoate		
20.74	0.52	2-cyclohexen-1-one,2-hydroxy-3-methyl-6-(1-methylethyl)-	30.78	0.25	2-oxabicyclo[3.3.0]oct-7-en-3-one,7-(1-hydroxypentyl)-
		2,6,10,10-tetramethyl-1-oxaspiro[4.5]decan-6-ol			5-(1-hydroxypentyl)-3,3a,4,6a-tetrahydro-2h-cyclopenta[b]furan-2-one
		3-bornanone, 6-hydroxy			9-methoxy-6-methyl-12,13-di oxo-tricyclo[7.3.1.01,6]tridecan-5-one
24.87	0.18	17-octadecynoic acid	30.86	0.75	1-propene-1,2,3-tricarboxylic acid,trimethyl ester
		9-octadecenoic acid (z)-	31.45	4.33	1-ethyl-3,cis-(1,1-dimethylethyl)-4,cis-methoxycyclohexan-1-ol
		z-(13,14-epoxy)tetradec-11-en-1-ol acetate	32.18	16.37	tributyl acetylcitrate
		cis-1,2-cyclododecanediol	35.91	0.49	3',8,8'-trimethoxy-3-piperidyl-2,2'-binaphthalene-1,1',4,4'-tetrone
		9,12-octadecadienoic acid (z,z)-	36.84	50.69	propanedioic acid, bis(2-methyl-2-propenyl)-, dimethyl ester
26.36	0.27	hexadecanoic acid, methylester	36.84	50.69	bis(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate
		pentadecanoic acid,14-methyl-, methyl ester			1,2-benzene dicarboxylic acid
		tetradecanoic acid,12-methyl-,methyl ester			1,2,4-benzenetriol
26.47	0.23	1,2-benzene dicarboxylic acid, butyl octyl ester	37.08	0.71	3',8,8'-trimethoxy-3-piperidyl-2,2'-binaphthalene-1,1',4,4'-tetrone
27.24	1.00	9-octadecenoic acid (z)-			1,2-benzene dicarboxylic acid
		n-hexadecanoic acid			9-(2',2'-dimethylpropanoilylhydrazono)-3,6-dichloro-2,7-bis-[2-(diethylamino)-ethoxy]fluorene
27.71	3.00	benzoic acid,3,4,5-trihydroxy,methyl ester	37.2	0.26	2,6-dimethyl-n-(2-methyl-phenyl)benzyl)aniline
		5-(1-hydroxypentyl)-3,3a,4,6a-tetrahydro-2h-cyclopenta[b]furan-2-one			3',8,8'-trimethoxy-3-piperidyl-2,2'-binaphthalene-1,1',4,4'-tetrone
27.77	1.26	benzoic acid, 3,4,5-trihydroxy-,methyl ester	37.2	0.26	1-propyl-3,6-diazahomoadamantan-9-ol
		5-(1-hydroxypentyl)-3,3a,4,6a-tetrahydro-2h-cyclopenta[b]furan-2-one			3-(4-methoxycarbonylmethyl-2-oxo-2,5-dihydro-1h-pyrrrol-3-yl)-propionic acid methyl ester
27.9	3.31	2,5-cyclohexadien-1-one,2,4,4-trimethoxy-	43.82	0.52	s-(tert-butyl)[2-(5-hydroxy-2-pentynyl)-3-oxocyclopentyl]ethanethioate
					tetracyclo[5.4.3.0(7,11)]tetradecane -2à-5ádíol-10-one, 1,4à,6,14-tetramethyl-4-vinyl-

RT= Rotation time

Table (6): Flower extract components of *Pelargonium graveolens* by using GC-MS analysis.

RT	Area %	Components	RT	Area %	Components
10.84	0.54	2,3-dihydro-benzofuran	30.8	0.15	r-limonene
		Phenol, 4-ethenyl-, acetate	30.91	1.77	1,2-cyclopropanedicarboxylic acid,3-(1-methylethenyl)-, diethyl ester
		6-methylene bicyclo[3.2.0]hept-3-en-2-one			9-methoxy-6-methyl-12,13-dioxa-tricyclo[7.3.1.01,6]tridecan-5-one
		3-(2-hydroxyphenyl)acrylic acid			2-benzoylbenzoic acid
10.93	0.37	Benzaldehyde, 2-methyl-	31.34	0.36	9-methoxy-6-methyl-12,13-dioxa-tricyclo[7.3.1.01,6]tridecan-5-one
11.04	0.24	Phenol, 4-ethenyl-, acetate			R-limonene
11.14	0.9	6-methylene bicyclo[3.2.0]hept-3-en-2-one			5-sec-butylpyrogallol
15.61	55.72	1,2,3-benzenetriol			
26.38	0.27	Pentadecanoic acid,14-methyl-, methyl ester	31.5	0.46	4-hydroxy-5-hydroxyimino-4-(2-imi nopropyl)-4,5,6,7-tetrahydrobenzofuroxan
		Cyclopentanetridecanoic acid, methyl ester			Bicyclo[2.2.1]heptane-2,3-dicarboxylic acid,2,3-dimethyl-, dimethylester, (endo,endo)-
		Hexadecanoic acid, methyl ester	32.1	0.21	1-propene-1,2,3-tricarboxylic acid,trimethyl ester
27.28	1.47	9-octadecenoic acid (z)-	35.88	5.53	4-hydroxy-5-hydroxyimino-4-(2-imi nopropyl)-4,5,6,7-tetrahydrobenzofuroxan
		N-hexadecanoic acid			Phenol, 3-pentadecyl-
28.13	1.12	2-oxabicyclo[3.3.0]oct-7-en-3-one,7-(1-hydroxypentyl)-a-tetrahydro-2h-cyclopen	36.06	0.94	Phenol, 3-pentadecyl-
		5-(1-hydroxypentyl)-3,3a,4,6 a-tetrahydro-2h-cyclopen ta[b]furan-2-one methyl			(z)-3-(pentadec-8-en-1-yl)phenol
		Ethyl 2-(acetylamino)-4,5-dimethyl-3-thiophene carboxylate			Propanedioic acid, bis(2-methyl-2-propenyl)-, dimethyl ester
		1,2-cyclopropane dicarboxylic acid,			2-methyl-z-4-tetradecene
28.21	0.23	Methyl 3,4,5-trihydroxy benzoate	36.19	1.06	Benzyl myristate
28.38	0.66	1,2-cyclopropanedi carboxylic acid,3-(1-methylethenyl)-, diethyl ester			2-nonenal, 2-pentyl-
28.45	0.18	2-oxabicyclo[3.3.0]oct-7-en-3-one,7-(1-hydroxypentyl)-	36.41	0.37	Propanedioic acid, bis(2-methyl-2-propenyl)-, dimethyl ester
		5-(1-hydroxypentyl)-3,3a,4,6 a-tetrahydro-2h-cyclopen ta[b]furan-2-one methyl			2-methyl-z-4-tetradecene
		3,4,5-trihydroxy benzoate			2-nonenal, 2-pentyl-
28.49	0.21	Methyl ethyl 3,4,5-trihydroxybenzoate	36.64	13.09	Bis(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate
28.62	0.42	2-oxabicyclo[3.3.0]oct-7-en-3-one,7-(1-hydroxypentyl)-			Phthalic acid, di(2-propylpentyl)ester
28.72	0.8	Benzoic acid, 3,4,5-trihydroxy-, methyl ester			1,2-benzene dicarboxylic acid
28.9	0.56	5-(1-hydroxypentyl)-3,3a,4,6 a-tetrahydro-2h-cyclopen ta[b]furan-2-one	37.24	0.34	Propanedioic acid,bis(2-methyl-2-propenyl)-, dimethyl ester
29.11	0.38	3,4,5-trihydroxybenzhydrazide	37.4	0.45	12-oxatricyclo[4.4.3.0(1,6)]tridecan e-3,11-dione
		1,2-cyclopropane dicarboxylic acid,3-(1-methylethenyl)-, diethyl ester	38.65	0.2	2-naphthol,1,2,3,4,4a,5,6,7-octahydro-4a-methyl
29.21	0.27	3,4,5-trihydroxybenzhydrazide	38.73	0.12	Butyl 9,12,15-octadecatrienoate
29.29	0.18	Ethyl 2-(acetylamino)-4,5-dimethyl-3-thiophenecarboxylate			Methyl 4,7,10,13-hexadecatetraenoate
29.48	1.09	Methane, [(1-ethynylcyclohexyl)oxy]methoxy-			Panaxjapyne a

Table (6): Continued

29.59	0.51	1,2-cyclopropanedicarboxylic acid,3-(1-methylethenyl)-, diethyl ester	38.78	0.34	Propanedioic acid, bis(2-methyl-2-propenyl)-, dimethyl ester
29.72	0.58	Ethyl 2-(acetylamino)-4,5-dimethyl-3-thiophenecarboxylate			Methyl 2-oxocyclododecanoate
		1,2-cyclopropanedicarboxylic acid,3-(1-methylethenyl)-, diethyl ester	39.1	2.45	(z)-3-(pentadec-8-en-1-yl)phenol
29.92	0.87	R-limonene			2,2-dimethyl-3-vinyl-bicyclo[2.2.1]heptane
30.15	0.3	5-(1-hydroxypentyl)-3,3a,4,6 a-tetrahydro-2h-cyclopenta[b]furan-2-one			
30.4	4.32	9,12-octadecadienoyl chloride, (z,z)-			
		(9e,12e)-9,12-octadecadienoyl chloride			
		8,11,14-eicosatrienoic acid, (z,z,z)-			
		Cyclohexanone, 2,2-dimethyl-5-(3-methoxyirany)-, [2â(r*),3â]-(.+.)-			

RT= Retention time

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